

Effect of anionic surfactant on binary complexes of L-arginine with Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}

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Abstract : Chemical speciation of binary complexes of L-arginine with Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} was investigated pH metrically in varying concentrations (0–2.5% w/v) of anionic surfactant-water mixtures at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ and temperature 303 K. The predominant complexes detected for these metal ions are MLH, ML₂H and ML₂. The trend in the variation of stability constants of the complexes with dielectric constant as well as composition of the medium was explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

Keywords : L-Arginine, binary complexes, chemical speciation.

Introduction

The physiological activities of L-arginine (Arg) with metal ions are associated with metabolic processes in liver^{1,2}. Amphiphilic molecules influence the bulk properties of physiological systems. They can solubilise, concentrate and compartmentalize ions and molecules³. With a view to study such effects in metal ion coordination with L-arginine the paper reports binary complex formation equilibria of L-arginine with Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions in SLS micellar medium of varying compositions.

Results and discussion

Effect of surfactant :

The effect of surfactant on complex equilibria and apparent shift in the magnitude of stability constants in micellar media compared to aqueous solution can be attributed to the creation of a concentration gradient of proton between the interface and the bulk solution⁴. Complex species with positive charge are stabilized by the anionic micelles due to the formation of ion pairs.

The variation of overall stability constant values or change in free energy with co-solvent content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic⁵. Stability constants of the metal-arginine complexes (Table 1) vary linearly as a function of composition of the medium. The linear variation indicates that electrostatic forces and decreased dielectric constant of the me-

Table 1. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants of L-arginine complexes in SLS-water mixtures
Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

%w/v SLS	log β ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃	
	Protonation constants of L-arginine pH range = 1.5–11.5			
0.0	11.46	20.67	23.25	
0.5	8.87	17.26	20.53	
1.0	8.84	16.92	19.99	
1.5	9.90	18.32	21.20	
2.0	10.33	19.28	22.87	
2.5	10.42	19.55	23.56	
% w/v SLS	MLH	ML ₂	ML ₂ H	
Co ^{II}	pH range = 1.70–10.7			
	0.0	14.58	10.97	21.21
	0.5	15.21	11.62	22.60
	1.0	15.53	11.84	22.79
	1.5	15.89	11.96	22.94
	2.0	16.25	12.12	23.25
	2.5	16.52	12.90	23.59
Cu ^{II}	pH range = 1.80–11.3			
	0.0	18.24	14.02	24.11
	0.5	19.16	15.57	25.48
	1.0	20.54	16.34	26.17
	1.5	20.89	16.93	26.81
	2.0	21.00	17.43	27.22
2.5	21.20	18.82	27.60	

Table-1 (contd.)

Zn ^{II}	pH range = 2.0–11.5		
0.0	14.68	11.95	22.77
0.5	15.07	12.10	23.09
1.0	15.53	12.50	23.62
1.5	15.85	12.77	23.81
2.0	16.47	12.92	23.99
2.5	16.81	13.85	24.26

Standard deviations (SD) : $\log \beta_1$ (0.01–0.07), $\log \beta_2$ (0.02–0.09), $\log \beta_3$ (0.02–0.12), $\log \beta_{MLH}$ (0.01–0.04), $\log \beta_{ML_2}$ (0.02–0.09) and $\log \beta_{ML_2H}$ (0.05–0.30).

dium^{6,7} are dominating the equilibrium process under the present experimental conditions.

Distribution diagrams :

Arginine (here after LH) occurs as LH_3^{2+} , LH_2^+ and LH in the pH-regions of 1.5–3.5, 2.5–9.0 and 8.0–11.5, respectively. The binary complex species are found to form MLH, ML_2H and ML_2 for all the three metal ions Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} . The formation of these complex species may be described according to following equilibria as the speciation curves (Fig. 1) imply (charges are omitted for simplicity) :

MLH and ML_2 species are formed to an extent of 60–80% at pH 6.0–11.0. The MLH species is suggested to form due to the interaction of active form (LH_2) of arginine

Fig. 1. Speciation curves of L-arginine- Co^{II} complexes in 1.5% w/v SLS-water mixture.

ine through equilibrium (1) and occur in the pH range 6.0–10.0. The ML_2H and ML_2 species are formed in the successive steps and occur in the pH ranges 8.5–11.0 and 9.5–11.0, respectively. As the speciation curves imply, ML_2 complexes result from deprotonation of the ML_2H complex (equilibrium (3)).

Experimental

Solution (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) of L-arginine (GR, E. Merck, Germany) was prepared by using triple distilled water. Solutions of Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} chlorides (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) were prepared by maintaining 0.05 mol dm^{-3} acid (HNO_3) to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts. SLS (AR, Qualigens, India) was used and its purity was checked by determining critical micellar concentration (CMC) conductometrically. The CMC value of SLS is $8.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Sodium nitrate was used to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method⁸.

Apparatus :

The alkalimetric data were obtained by using calibrated ELICO (Model LI-120) pH-meter (readability 0.01). The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred micellar solution containing inert electrolyte ($NaNO_3$). The effects of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor⁹. For the determination of stability constants of metal-ligand binary species, initially titrations of strong acid with alkali were carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved.

Procedure :

All the titrations have been carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations of SLS (0.0–2.5% w/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm^{-3} with sodium nitrate at 303 K. In each of the titrations, the titrant consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 cm^3 . Titrations with different ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.5, 1 : 5) of metal-to-ligand were carried out with 0.4 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere¹⁰.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD¹¹ was used to calcu-

late the correction factor. By using the pH-metric titration data, the binary stability constants were calculated with the computer program MINQUAD75¹² which exploits the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of binary systems, the correction factor and the protonation constants of arginine are fixed. The variation of stability constants with the mole fraction of the surfactant was analyzed on electrostatic/non-electrostatic, solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

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